

Variability study of yield and development of yardstick of CV (%) for mango crop experiment

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Abstract

Large number of field experiments were conducted every year at different locations with different objectives, set of treatments, number of replications and different experimental plot size. This study was carried out to develop the yard stick of CV% for accepting the results of mango crop experiment. The secondary data regarding mango yield of 158 field experiments conducted at various research stations of South Gujarat region of last 15 years were utilized for development of yardstick. The yardstick of CV for field experiments was worked out by using average upper fiducial limit of CV for each of the 158 experiments were worked out separately and then average of these upper fiducial limits was computed. The upper fiducial limit of 95% and 99% worked out by using the theory of truncated t-distribution as described by (Johnson and Welch, 1939). The results implied that most of the experiments were conducted in single factor Randomized Block Design. Experiments whose number of treatments were between 6-10 showed lower CV (%) as compared to overall average CV (%). The experiments conducted with 3, 4 and 5 replications provide lower CV (%). The experiments conducted at RHRS, Navsari had less CV (%) as compared to AES, Paria. Higher CV (%) in experiments reduces the power of F-test. The yardstick of CV (%) for accepting the results of mango experiments in South Gujarat region should be less than 29 per cent for yield character of mango.

Keywords: Yardstick, Coefficient of variation, Mango, Fiducial limit.

1. Introduction

Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) belongs to family Anacardiaceae and it is the most important commercially grown fruit crop of the country. It is known as ‘king of fruits’. India has the richest collection of mango cultivars. The experimental data provide information regarding controlled (treatment effect) and uncontrolled (Environmental effect). This uncontrolled variation is expressed as experimental error and it is measured through coefficient of variation (CV%). Gomez and Gomez (1984) reported that CV% varies greatly with the type of experiment, type of crop and type of character. They stated that the acceptable range of CV is 6 to 8% for varietal trials, 10 to 12% for fertilizer trials and 13 to 15% for insecticidal and herbicidal trials. There are large number of experiments conducted every year at different locations. The acceptable range of CV advocated by various workers is based on the experience with very limited number of experiments. There is need to develop a yardstick for CV based on theory and also on a large number experiments conducted under different situations. The present paper deals with this aspect (Johnson and Welch,

1939) reported that for a normal distribution, the ratio of mean to standard deviation should be of the order of 3 or more. Further, they mentioned that 33% has often been stated as the permissible upper fiducial limit of CV. Tyagi *et al.*, (1973) and Patel *et al.*, (1978) pointed out that CV obtained for the crops under study was found to be considerably higher than those reported from the uniformity trials. They stated that the yardstick for accepting experimental results should be worked out using CV observed in the experiments rather than in the uniformity trials. (Bajpai and Nigam, 1980) This study was carried out to develop the yardstick of CV (%) for accepting the results of mango crop experiment utilizing the mango yield data of field experiments conducted at various research stations of South Gujarat region with two objectives:

1. To study the variability (CV%) of mango crop experiments conducted at South Gujarat region
2. To develop yardstick of CV (%) for accepting or rejecting the results of the filed experiments of mango crop at South Gujarat region.

Figure 1: Map of study area

2. Materials and Methods

The secondary data regarding mango yield of 158 mango experiments were collected from Regional Horticulture Research Station (RHRS), NAU, Navsari and Agriculture Experimental Station (AES), NAU, Paria of last 15 years as depicted in Figure 1. These data were utilized for the variability study and for develop yardstick of CV (%) for accepting or rejecting the results of the filed experiments of mango crop at South Gujarat region. Information on design of experiment, number of treatments, replication, SEm (\pm) and CD @ 5% level of probability, plot size and CV% were subjected to statistical analysis. CV is a ratio of standard deviation (σ) and general mean (\bar{X}) and formula is as below:

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{X}} \quad \dots(1)$$

The distribution of \bar{X} and σ have simple forms and student's t-distribution provides complete solution for testing the hypothesis or estimating fiducial limits relating to either \bar{X} or σ , singly. But t distribution cannot be used for $CV = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{X}}$. Instead of this, McKay (1932) used non-central t-distribution providing fiducial limits of CV.

Let z be a quantity distributed normally about zero mean with unit standard deviation and let w be a quantity distributed independently as χ^2/f , with f degrees of freedom. Then, t is defined by the following equation:

$$t = \frac{z + \delta}{\sqrt{w}} \quad \dots(2)$$

Where, δ is some constant, then t is distributed in a manner depending only on δ and f .

This is a non-central t distribution. When δ equals to zero, the distribution is the familiar to Student's t-distribution.

Let an estimate of sample coefficient of variation V

$$v = s/\bar{X}$$

Now one may write,

$$\frac{\sqrt{n}}{v} = \frac{\sqrt{n}\bar{X}}{s} = \frac{\sqrt{n}(\bar{X}-\mu)}{\sigma} + \frac{\sqrt{n}\mu}{\sigma} + \frac{s}{\sigma} \quad \dots(3)$$

It appears from comparison with eq. (2) that $\frac{\sqrt{n}}{v}$ is distributed as non-central t with $f=(n-1)$ and $\sigma\sqrt{n/V}$. This distribution can be used for

test of significance and for providing fiducial limits of V (*i.e.* CV), as is done for μ .

Since the objective was to work out the yardstick based on CV, the upper fiducial limit of CV using non-central t-distribution was estimated following the procedure given by Johnson and Welch (1939). The procedure is as below:

$$i. \quad CV = \frac{\sqrt{\text{Error Means Square}}}{\text{General Mean}}$$

Now the upper fiducial limit of CV is:

$$CV_{UL} = \frac{\sqrt{n}}{\delta} (f, t_0, \epsilon) \quad \text{where, } t_0 = \frac{\sqrt{n}}{CV}$$

$$ii. \quad y = \left(1 + \frac{t_0^2}{2f}\right)^{-1/2} \quad \text{or}$$

$$y' = \frac{t_0}{\sqrt{2f}} \left(1 + \frac{t_0^2}{2f}\right)^{-1/2}$$

Consider Y and Y' according to value of $t_0/\sqrt{2f}$ is greater than or less than 0.75.

Consider Y' , if $t_0/\sqrt{2f}$ lies between -0.75 and 0.75 , otherwise consider Y .

iii. If $f > 9$, calculate

iv. Select desired probability level of confidence, *i.e.* ϵ and obtain λ (f, t_0, ϵ) from the table in (Johnson and Welch, 1939) interpolating with respect to the quantities obtained in (ii) and (iii).

v. Calculate δ (f, t_0, ϵ) =

$$t_0 - \lambda \left(1 + \frac{t_0^2}{2f}\right)^{-1/2}$$

3. Results and Discussion

The results presented in Table 1 showed the upper fiducial limit of CV (%) for different designs of experiment of mango crop in South Gujarat. The result revealed that average CV (%) was 21.66 for all the 158 experiments and the upper fiducial limit at 95% and 90% were 28.37 and 26.62, respectively. Most of the experiments (78%) were conducted with one factor Randomized Block Design and about 20% of them had higher CV% than fiducial limit (28.37). Around 18% experiments were conducted in two-factor Randomized Block Design and among these, 55% experiments had higher CV (%) than fiducial limit. All the Experiments conducted in Split plot design had CV (%) below the fiducial limit. Motaka *et al.* (2025) also reported that maximum tobacco experiments were conducted in Randomized Block design (RBD) and very few experiment

showed higher CV (%) than fiducial limit of CV (%). Motaka *et al.* (2016) also observed similar type of trend in wheat experiments where, most of the wheat experiments were conducted in

RBD and experiments conducted in Split Plot Design (SPD) and RBD showed 0.14 and 0.23 proportion of CV (%) compared to FRBD, respectively.

Table 1: Upper fiducial limit of CV (%) for different design of mango experiments in South Gujarat

Designs	No. of Experiments	Mean CV (%)	UL		CV (%) >28.37	
			(0.05)	(0.10)	No. of Expt.	Proportion
RBD	123	19.35	26.22	24.40	25	0.20
FRBD	29	33.10	39.75	38.15	16	0.55
SPD	06	13.88	17.41	16.53	00	0.00
Total/Avg.	158	21.66	28.37	26.62		

Number of treatments were categorised into different groups and upper fiducial limit of CV (%) for different number of treatments wise depicted in Table 2. The results revealed that CV (%) was found higher for treatment group 'less than 6' and '11 to 15' than overall average CV i.e. 21.66%. Treatment group 'Less than 6' had highest proportion of experiments whose CV (%) were higher than fiducial limits due to less error degree of freedom and improper conductance of experiments. Even number of treatments between 11 to 15 also showed higher CV (%) might be due to violation of any principles of experimental design.

Table 2: Upper fiducial limit of CV% for different treatments of mango experiments in South Gujarat

No. of Treatments	No. of Experiments	Mean CV (%)	UL		CV% >28.37	
			(0.05)	(0.10)	No. of Expt.	Proportion
Less than 6	18	30.44	41.89	38.82	09	0.50
6 to 10	93	17.83	24.33	22.60	15	0.16
11 to 15	41	26.84	32.46	31.10	16	0.39
21 to 25	06	19.33	22.50	21.76	01	0.16
Total/Avg.	158	21.66	28.37	26.62		

Replication is an important principle of experimental design and it control the one way variation in experimental material by proper blocking. The result regarding upper fiducial limit of CV% for different number of replications of mango experiments were presented in Table 3. It revealed that around 52% experiments were conducted with three replications followed by 20% with four replications. Among the different number of replications, experiments with 15 replications provide highest (100%) proportion of experiments whose CV% were more than fiducial limits. It might be due to higher yield variation observed for replication to replication and less plants were selected for experimental plot. Experiments with six replications also provide around 70% proportion of higher CV than fiducial limits.

Table 3: Upper fiducial limit of CV% for different replications of mango experiments in South Gujarat

No. of Replications	No. of Experiments	Mean CV (%)	UL		CV% >28.37	
			(0.05)	(0.10)	No. of Expt.	Proportion
2	1	24.68	37.58	33.87	0	0.00
3	83	17.22	23.44	21.79	12	0.14
4	31	16.87	21.51	20.34	4	0.13
5	14	18.66	25.66	23.8	3	0.21
6	23	38.36	46.04	44.21	16	0.70
15	6	50.33	68.99	63.95	6	1.00
Total/Avg.	158	21.66	28.37	26.62		

Location is also an effective factor for causing variation in experiment. Location to location the variation in experimental units were different due to different climatic and physical condition. Table 4 showed information regarding upper fiducial limit of CV% for different location of mango experiments. The result revealed that experiments conducted at RHRS, Navsari had average 14.55% CV whereas AES, Paria had 24.32% CV. It might be due to environmental condition or variation in selected plants or less number of plants were included in experimental plot. Variation among the location were also reported by Motaka *et al.*, (2025)

Table 4: Upper fiducial limit of CV% for different location of mango experiments in South Gujarat

Locations	No. of Experiments	Mean CV (%)	UL		CV% >28.37	
			(0.05)	(0.10)	No. of Expt.	Proportion
RHRS, Navsari	43	14.55	19.27	18.04	4	0.09
AES, Paria	115	24.32	31.77	29.83	37	0.32
Total/Avg.	158	21.66	28.37	26.62		

F-test is used for detection of difference in treatment means and it is ratio of treatment mean square (MS_T) to the error means square (MS_E). Coefficient of variation is an error term and it cause effects on power of F-test because experiments with higher CV had higher error means square (MS_E) and it resulted in lower F value tends to be non-significant effect. Table 5 presented information regarding power of F-test that was influenced by CV% and graphically presented in Figure 2. The result showed that the average ratio was observed 0.35 and this ratio increased with increase in CV%. The result clearly showed that the experiments with more than 28.37% CV failed to detect differences in treatment means and had higher chances of non-significant result. Similar findings of reduction of F-test as CV (%) increased was also observed by Patel *et al.*, (2001), Darji *et al.*, (2010), Motaka *et al.*, (2016) and Motaka *et al.*, (2025).

Table 5: Power of F-test as influenced by CV%

CV%	No. of Experiment	F-test		
		Significant	Non-significant	Ratio
1 to 11	42	35	7	0.20
11 to 21	60	41	19	0.46
21 to 31	20	15	5	0.33
31 to 41	17	14	3	0.21
41 to 51	8	5	3	0.60
51 to 61	7	5	2	0.40
61 to 71	3	2	1	0.50
71 to 81	1	0	1	1.00
Total	158	117	41	0.35

Figure 2: Power of F-test as influenced by CV%

4. Conclusion

Most of the experiments were conducted in single factor Randomized Block Design. Number of treatments between 6 to 10 and 21 to 25 showed lower CV (%) as compared to overall average CV (%). The experiments conducted with 3, 4 and 5 replications provide lower CV (%). The experiments conducted at RHRS, Navsari had less CV (%) as compared to ARS, Paria. Higher CV (%) in experiments reduces the power of F-test. When the coefficient of variation for mango experiments exceeds 29 per cent, the experimental finding should not be considered for any scientific purpose.

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